

СЎЗ САЊАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА | INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

№4 (2023) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-9297-2023-4>

Бош муҳаррир:

Тўхтасинов Илҳом

п.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Бош муҳаррир ўринбосари:

Главный редактор:

Тухтасинов Илхом

д.п.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Заместитель главного редактора:

Editor in Chief:

Tuhtasinov Ilhom

DSc. Professor (Uzbekistan)

Deputy Chief Editor

ТАҲРИРИЙ МАСЛАҲАТ КЕНГАШИ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Ўзбекистон)

Якуб Умарўғли

ф.ф.д., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

ф.ф.д., профессор (Озарбайжон)

Бокиева Гуландом

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Миннуллин Ким

ф.ф.д., профессор (Татаристон)

Махмудов Низомиддин

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Керимов Исмаил

ф.ф.д., профессор (Россия)

Жўраев Маматкул

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Куренов Рахиммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистон)

Кристофер Жеймс Форт

Мичиган университети (АҚШ)

Умархўжаев Мухтор

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Болтабоев Ҳамидулла

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Дўстмухаммедов Хуршид

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Сиддикова Ирода

ф.ф.д., профессор (Ўзбекистон)

Шиукашвили Тамар

ф.ф.д. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат

масъул котиб, PhD, доцент
(Ўзбекистон)

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ

Назаров Бахтиёр

академик. (Узбекистан)

Якуб Умар оглы

д.ф.н., профессор (Туркия)

Алмаз Улви Биннатова

д.ф.н., профессор (Азербайджан)

Бакиева Гуландом

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Миннуллин Ким

д.ф.н., профессор (Татарстан)

Махмудов Низомиддин

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Керимов Исмаил

д.ф.н., профессор (Россия)

Джураев Маматкул

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Куренов Рахыммаед

к.ф.н. (Туркменистан)

Кристофер Джеймс Форт

Университет Мичигана (США)

Умархаджаев Мухтар

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Мирзаев Ибодулло

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Балтабоев Ҳамидулла

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Дустмухаммедов Хуршид

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Лиходзиевский А.С.

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Сиддикова Ирода

д.ф.н., профессор (Узбекистан)

Шиукашвили Тамар

д.ф.н. (Грузия)

Туробов Бекпулат

отв. секретарь, PhD, доцент
(Узбекистан)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bakhtiyor Nazarov

academician. (Uzbekistan)

Yakub Umarogli

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Turkey)

Almaz Ulvi Binnatova

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Azerbaijan)

Bakieva Gulandom

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Minnulin Kim

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Tatarstan)

Mahmudov Nizomiddin

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kerimov Ismail

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Russia)

Juraev Mamatkul

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Kurenov Rakhimmamed

Ph.D. Ass. Prof. (Turkmenistan)

Christopher James Fort

University of Michigan (USA)

Umarkhodjaev Mukhtar

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Mirzaev Ibodulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Boltaboev Hamidulla

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Dustmuhammedov Khurshid

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Lixodzievsky A.S.

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Siddiqova Iroda

Doc. of philol. scien., prof. (Uzbekistan)

Shiukashvili Tamar

Doc. of philol. scien. (Georgia)

Turobov Bekpulat

PhD Ass. prof. Senior Secretary
(Uzbekistan)

PageMaker | Верстка | Саҳифаловчи: Хуршид Мирзахмедов

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz

ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,

улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz

Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,

Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.

Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz

Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

1. Xasanova Gulrux Xayrullayevna LINGVOMADANIYATSHUNOSLIKDA NOVERBAL VOSITALARNING O‘RNI.....	5
2. Akhunkhodjaeva N.T., Rozmetova Z.Sh. AN INTERNATIONAL LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY TESTS: A HELPFUL TOOL OR MISLEADING CONCEPT?.....	12
3. Axmedova Aziza Komilovna XX ASR TONGIDA AMERIKA ADABIYOTIDA ZAMONAVIY AYOL OBRAZI.....	16
4. Maftuna Mahmudova Hamza qizi AXBOROT TAHDIDLARIDA MANIPULYATSIYA TUSHUNCHASINING ILMIY-NAZARIY TASNIFI.....	21
5. Мустафаев Шахбоз Бахтиёрвич, Mustafayev Shakhboz Bakhtiyorovich, Mustafayev Shaxboz Vaxtiyorovich ЯЗЫК И ВИРТУАЛЬНАЯ КОММУНИКАЦИЯ ЧЕРЕЗ ИНТЕРНЕТ: ОТЧУЖДЕНИЕ ЛИЧНОСТИ.....	27
6. Содикова Назокат Гафоровна СТРУКТУРНО-СЕМАНТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ГЛАГОЛЬНЫХ АНАЛИТИЧЕСКИХ КОНСТРУКЦИЙ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ.....	35
7. Ibadova Nafisa Axmatilloevna THE ROLE OF KHALED HOSSEINI'S CREATIVITY IN THE FORMATION OF THE LITERARY CULTURE OF CENTRAL ASIA.....	40
8. Vositov Otabek Toxirjonovich TILSHUNOSLIKDA FRAZEO-SEMANTIK MAYDON MUAMMOSINING O‘RGANILISHI.....	44
9. Saloxiddinov Manuchehr Sharofiddinovich TURLI TILLAR TIZIMIDA FAZA FE‘LLARI.....	49
10. Очилова Ноила Фармоновна ИРРЕАЛИС КОНЦЕПТУАЛЛАШУВИНИНГ АСОСИЙ БЕЛГИЛАРИ.....	56
11. Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna TIL VA DINNING O‘ZARO ALOQALARINI O‘RGANISH.....	62
12. Шаропова Нилуфар Бахшилло кизи ИСКУССТВО ПЕРЕВОДА И СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ К СЛОЖНЫМ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫМ ТЕКСТАМ.....	67
13. Расулов Нормурод Атакулович ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДА РЕАЛИС/ИРРЕАЛИС ҲОДИСАСИНИ ТАШКИЛ ҚИЛУВЧИ БИРЛИКЛАРНИНГ ЛЕКСИК-СЕМАНТИК СТРУКТУРАЛ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ.....	74
14. Nilufar Abduraxmonova, Saodat Boysariyeva TABIIY TILNI QAYTA ISHLASHDA (NLP) OKKAZIONALIZMLARNING MORFEM TAHLILI.....	80
15. Xolova Muyassar Abdulhakimovana O‘ZBEK SHEVASI ONLAYN LUG‘ATINING MA’LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA QIPCHOQ LAHJASINING INGLIZ TILIGA TARJIMASI.....	87
16. Saliyeva Nigora Ikromovna, Djurayev Dilshod Mamadiyarovich O‘ZBEK TALABALARINING HSK 5-DARAJASI 写作 “YOZUV” BO‘LIMINI TOPSHIRISHDA YO‘L QO‘YGAN LEKSIK XATOLARI TAHLILI.....	98
17. Раъно Мардонова СИФАТЛАШ ВА ЭПИТЕТНИНГ ҚИЁСИГА ДОИР.....	106
18. Nizomova Mohinur Baratboyevna PEDAGOGIKAGA OID TERMINLARDA PRAGMALINGVISTIK YONDASHUV TAHLILI (INGLIZ VA O‘ZBEK TILLARI MISOLIDA).....	111

19. Aslanova Hafiza Abdurahimovna TURKIY VA FORSIY ADABIYOTLARDA TASAVVUFIIY HIKOYATLAR (HOJA ADABIY MEROSI).....	119
20. Зиёева Дилноза Анваровна ИНГЛИЗ ВА ЎЗБЕК ТИЛЛАРИДАГИ НУТҚИЙ ФАОЛИЯТ ФЕЪЛЛАРИНИНГ ПАРАДИГМАТИК ТАҲЛИЛИ.....	125
21. Зияев Аваз, Илхом Тожибоев КОНЦЕПТ “КРАСОТА” И ЕГО УНИВЕРСАЛЬНАЯ ПРИРОДА.....	130
22. Исаева Шоира Махаматовна ВЛИЯНИЕ СРЕДНЕАЗИАТСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ В ПРОИЗВЕДЕНИИ КУТАДГУ БИЛИГ ЮСУФА ХОС ХАДЖИБА.....	136
23. Юсупова Гулчехра Алишеровна ЎЗБЕК ТИЛШУНОСЛИГИДА НУТҚИЙ ЭТИКЕТ МАСАЛАЛАРИ.....	140
24. Shamuradova Naima Muxtarovna KAUZALLIKNING INGLIZ VA O'ZBEK TILLARIDA IFODALANISHI.....	145
25. Kurbonova Gulnoza Irkinovna, Jalolova Laylo Shavkatovna KAVABATA YASUNARINING “OYNADAGI OY” ASARIDA REALIYALAR TAHLILI.....	152
26. Каххорова Gulrux Shavkatovna, Kakhkhorova Gulrux Shavkatovna, Каххорова Гульрух Шавкатовна O'ZBEK VA INGLIZ TILLARIDA YORDAMCHI SO'Z TURKUMLARINING ASOSIY VAZIFALARI.....	158
27. Allaberdiyev Alijon BUXORO O'G'UZ SHEVALARIDA BOG'LOVCHILARNING QO'LLANISHI.....	164
28. Sodikov Dilshodbek Kobilovich “ANOR” ASARI TARJIMALARINING O'ZIGA HOS LINGVISTIK VA LINGUOKULTUROLOGIK TADQIQI.....	168
29. Qobilov Mirziyo Eshnozovich KASALLIK NOMLARIGA OID TERMINLARNING LINGVOSTILISTIK XUSUSIYATI.....	173
30. Khudaiberdieva Dilfuza Mukhtarovna IMAGERY AS A UNIT OF FIGURATIVENESS AND EXPRESSIVENESS.....	180
31. Мавлянова Умида Ходжакбаровна ХИТОЙ ТИЛИДА НУМЕРОЛОГИК СОН ВА СИМВОЛЛАР МУТАНОСИБЛИГИ.....	185
32. Turniyozova Dildora Bekhzod kizi STUDIES OF PERFORMATIVITY IN LINGUISTICS.....	193
33. Absalamov Xiloliddin Uchkunovich INGLIZ TILIDA YOZMA NUTQ KOMPETENTSIYASINING TADQIQI.....	199

ISSN: 2181-9297

www.tadqiqot.uz

Sadriiddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna
Samarqand davlat chet tillar instituti,
ingliz tili nazariyasi va adabiyoti kafedrası

TIL VA DINNING O'ZARO ALOQALARINI O'RGANISH

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10157544>

ANNOTATSIYA

Ilohiyot – tilshunoslikning dunyoviy, xalqaro va diniy bo'lmagan sohasi. Diniy dunyoqarashning tilda aks etishi ilohiyot fanining predmeti hisoblanadi. Buni bir necha usul bilan o'rganish mumkin. Birinchidan, bu tilning tabiatini ontologik talqin qilish masalalari. Diniy dunyoqarash alohida tadqiqot sohasidir. Ko'pgina tushunchalar, hodisalar va narsalar diniy kontekstda alohida ma'noga ega. Ikkinchidan, bu diniy muloqotni tahlil qilish bilan bog'liq (mo'minlarning Xudo bilan munosabatlari; dindorlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar; dindorlar va ateistlar o'rtasidagi munosabatlar; ateistlarning diniy muhitdagi xatti-harakatlari va boshqalar). Nutq xulq-atvori taktikasini va nutq odob-axloq formulalarini solishtirganda, dindorlar va ateistlar yoki turli dinlarga e'tiqod qiluvchilarning kommunikativ xatti-harakatlaridagi farqlar aniq ko'rinadi. Lingvistik personologiya nuqtai nazaridan, diniy lingvistik shaxsni dunyoviy va diniy muloqot kontekstida o'rganish muhimdir. Uchinchidan, asosiy e'tibor diniy matnlarni o'rganish, ularning tipologiyasi va tasnifi, kanonik va nokanonik matnlarni farqlash, teologik leksemalarning semantik sohasiga e'tibor qaratishdir.

Kalit so'zlar: tilshunoslik, ilohiyotshunoslik, diniy lingvistik shaxs, diniy va teologik jihatlar, dunyoning diniy tasviri.

Садриддинзода Сафия Шахобиддиновна,
Самарканд Государственный институт иностранных языков,
преподаватель кафедры теории английского языка и литературы

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВЗАИМОСВЯЗИ ЯЗЫКА И РЕЛИГИИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Теология - это отрасль языкознания, которая является светской, интернациональной и нерелигиозной. Отражение религиозного мировоззрения в языке является предметом изучения богословия. Этому можно научиться несколькими способами. Во-первых, это вопросы онтологического истолкования природы языка. Религиозное миропонимание представляет собой особую область исследований. Многие понятия, события и вещи в религиозном контексте имеют особое значение. Во-вторых, это связано с анализом религиозной коммуникации. При сопоставлении речевых тактик, формул речевого этикета можно проследить различия в коммуникативном поведении верующих и атеистов (то есть носителей религиозного сознания), верующих разных религий. С точки зрения лингвистики (индивидуального (частного) использования языка) важно изучение религиозной языковой

личности в контексте религиозной и светской коммуникации. В-третьих, большое внимание уделяется анализу религиозных текстов, их классификации и типологии, канонических и неканонических текстов, в центре исследования которого семантическое поле богословских лексем.

Ключевые слова: языкознание, теолингвистика, религиозная языковая личность, религиозно - богословные аспекты, религиозная картина мира.

Sadriddinzoda Safiya Shaxobiddinovna

Teacher of Samarkand state institute of foreign languages

STUDYING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN LANGUAGE AND RELIGION

ANNOTATION

Theology might be learned in many branches. It's considered to be non-religious, international and secular. The subject of it is to learn reflection of the religious worldview. Firstly, these are issues of ontological interpretation of the nature of language. Religious worldview is a special area of research. Secondly, it is connected with the analysis of religious communication. When tactics are compared in speech-behavioral way, formulas of speech etiquette, (that is, carriers of religious consciousness), Different believer are might be recognized. From the point of view of linguistic (individual speech usage), it is important to study the religious linguistic personality in the context of secular and religious communication. Thirdly, the main attention is paid to the study of religious texts, their typology and classification, the distinction between canonical and non-canonical texts, focusing on the semantic field of theological lexemes.

Keywords: linguistics, ethnolinguistics, religious linguistic personality, religious and theological aspects, religious picture of the world.

During our study, we also took into account the fact that the word is considered the main link in lexicology. And there are also the main tasks of lexicology, which consist of the seismological characteristics of words and phrases, determining the distinguishing features of lexical and phraseological units, describing units with a word and a free phrase, and also analyzing the laws of words and phrases. In this regard, there are several approaches to the interpretation of the concept of demonological vocabulary. Our research interest is directed to the study of the lexical-grammatical tier of religious vocabulary.

Theolinguistics is the subject where clearly is shown religious, mythological, artistic and philosophical aspects of the language. It's the best way to understand the ways. This must be understood at least in the most elementary and general form, because firstly, in the process of creating theology in the creative minds of "theolinguists", two different forms of thinking are dominant - scientific and religious-theological. After all, theology shows that it represents a unique type of science, even if it is complicated by the addition of religious and theological aspects of understanding the world of reality.

Dante Alighieri points out that people cannot understand each other only with the help of gestures or body movements; in order to convey their thoughts to each other, it is necessary to have a reasonable and sensitive sign. This is how the language became familiar. Dante believed that language has a two-sided nature: sensual, which is revealed in its sound, and rational, which is manifested in its ability to designate and mean something. Diderot believes that the needs of society contributed to the development of language, but man owes its appearance to God. L.Jacob tries to explain the concept of language through the concept of a sign in general and the definition of its role in the mental life of a person. He calls language "every system of such signs that can be used at will to communicate thoughts" After all, the main task of linguistics is the study of each known language in its internal connections, in its relationships, because its components. Belinsky claims that contemporary with the birth of thought, man began to speak he began to think. De Saussure compares it to chess... language is a system subject to its own order. Each generation receives a ready-made language from the

previous one, but these ready-made forms contain everything for the renewal of the language and its eternal movement as a result of human creativity. According to Rizhsky, words are the signs of our thoughts. The properties of the thing designated must be in its image if it can express them. Consequently, everything that is essential and always belongs to our thoughts must be essential and certainly in our words. Linguistics is one of the most ancient sciences of our time. E. Sapir believes that language is a huge socializing force, perhaps the greatest of all existing ones. This means not only the obvious fact that without language meaningful social communication is hardly possible, but also the fact that common speech acts as a kind of potential symbol of social solidarity of all speakers of a given language.

According to A.K. Gadomsky, who shares this understanding, "linguistics arose as theo-linguistics and only over the centuries acquired a secular character." Theolinguistics is a type of scientific discipline that includes the scientific and religious-theological branches of the worldview of reality. Language and speech have an undeniable relationship and are closely intertwined in all spheres of human life. According to W. von Humboldt, if language contributes to the formation of the human spirit, then in our opinion the second category is religion. Since, it is precisely this that is an important category of development and formation of a full-fledged worldview. Religion is an integral part of the culture and social consciousness of an ethnic group. This is due to the fact that religion, being one of the earliest forms of social consciousness, significantly influenced and continues to influence the culture and social way of life of any people, determining its national picture of the world, a special way of perceiving the world, moral consciousness, its spiritual and national view of the surrounding reality.

According to A.K. Gadomsky, the tasks of theolinguistics are the following:

1. Selection of material from relevant sources, texts
2. Differentiation of the obtained material
3. Systematization of the received material
4. Integration of the received material

According to I. Baerova and Y. Puzyrina, in the narrow sense of the word, religious language is the language of moral and dogmatic theology, as well as ritual language, the language of personal prayers, sacred texts (the Bible), sermons, and works of religious fiction.

In a broad sense, religious language refers to spoken language containing statements about God and the relationship of people to God, as well as the language of texts on a religious topic - for example, texts on history, sociology and psychology of religion. Admitting the possibility of linguistic research carried out on the material of the language of a particular religion, we, however, believe that they should be carried out only within the framework of a special linguistic discipline, which can be theolinguistics. This is due to the fact that a linguistic discipline aimed at studying the relationship and interaction of language and religion should be universal in nature and unite all studies that, to one degree or another, reflect the interaction of language and religion. In this regard, the term "theolinguistics," which combines both theology and linguistics in its name, in our opinion, is the most acceptable and optimal. According to V.I. Yurchenko, "a thinking person wants to the idea of God fit into his scientific idea of the world...he needs this idea in order to complete the scientific picture of the world" [Yurchenko, 1992, p. 6].

According to A.F.Losev

"Religion is, first of all, a certain kind of life. Religion is the fulfillment of a worldview, the material substance of morality, the real affirmation of feelings..." [Losev, 1994, p. 97]; For the Uzbek mentality, the

study of theolinguistics is associated with the study of the Holy Quran and Hadith, as well as the study of the works of such great scientists as Imom Abu Abdulloh Muhammad ibn Ismoil al-Bukhoriy, Imom Muhammad ibn Iso at-Termiziy, Imom Ahmad ibn Shuaib Khurosoniy Nasai, Imom Abu Mansur Motrudiy, Imom Abu Lais Nasr ibn Muhammad al-Samarkandiy, Imom Zhorulloh Abul Kosim Mahmud Ibn Umar az-Zamakhshariy, Imom Fakhridin ar-Roziy wa Imom Abul Barakot Abdulloh ibn Ahmad an-Nasafiy [Mavlonov, 2019]. The religion of each world is also a system of beliefs, which includes moral norms, rules of behavior, certain rituals and belief in the supernatural.

It originated in ancient times after the appearance of language, but at the same time it had a tremendous influence on the formation of language. The initial appearance of language, stages of formation and modern linguistics is a large school that is constantly in the process of development. Religion has a similar development trend, from the emergence stage to modern theology. If totemism and animism are an early form of religion, in the process of development it is also complicated by paganism, polytheism – polytheism (Ancient Egypt, India, Greece, Rome, ancient Germans, ancient Rus', ancient Sogdiana), which is replaced by a period of worship of one single God – monotheism. Such leading religions of the world as Judaism, Christianity and Islam have the above characteristics. There is nothing singular in language; each individual element manifests itself only as a part of the whole. Language in its most diverse applications can be understood only when the “differences in the organism”, its relationships, are considered, for in the relationships of the concepts that make up language, all its genius is manifested. Language is presented as an organism in which one element cannot be corroded and where even the smallest detail plays an important role. There is still debate about the origin of the language and there are many hypotheses unjustified by science. But at the same time, from the appearance of language to language has undergone great changes in its modern development, both in terms of practice and theory.

Linguistics
External linguistics
Internal linguistics
Phonetics
Morphology
syntax
Lexcology
Theoretical linguistics
applied linguistics

The same pattern can be traced in modern religious views. If in Christianity, Judaism and Islam, at the very top there is a single patron, the Almighty. Then he has his messengers. In Christianity it is Jesus Christ, in Judaism Moses and in Islam Muhammad (saw). Each of these prophets gave holy books to humanity, in which a number of rules were written for the righteous life of man. Each of the above religions has its own angels and demons, the functionality of which is no different from each other. Next comes the responsibility of the person (according to the religious worldview, obedience to the laws written in the holy book, respect for God, his messenger and angels). That is, we can consider the above system as one single organism, in which each element is an integral part. Currently, the following problems are at the center of theolinguistic research. The same pattern can be traced in modern religious views. If in Christianity, Judaism and Islam, at the very top there is a single patron, the Almighty. Then he has his messengers. In Christianity it is Jesus Christ, in Judaism Moses and in Islam Muhammad (saw). Each of these prophets gave holy books to humanity, in which a number of rules were written for the righteous life of man. Each of the above religions has its own angels and demons, the functionality of which is no different from each other. Next comes the responsibility of the person (according to the religious worldview, obedience to the laws written in the holy book, respect for God, his messenger and angels). That is, we can consider the above system as one single organism, in which each element is an integral part. Like linguistics, theolinguistics can be divided into general and specific theolinguistics. Generally theolinguistics must deal with general issues, categories, universals - in other words, manifestations that can occur in any language and can be associated with any religion and denomination. Such general issues include problems of the history of linguistics, the theoretical description of religious language in the narrow and broad sense of the

term, the terminology of theolinguistics and a number of others. Particular theolinguistics must examine the manifestations of a particular religion in a particular language or a particular problem reflected in a particular language (languages). For example, studying the functions of quotations in Church Slavonic in the genre of sermons delivered in modern Russian in the Orthodox tradition. Despite the polar oppositeness of the plans for the content of language and religion, there are complex relationships between them - due to their deep rootedness in the human consciousness, rootedness that goes back to the origins of humanity in man.

Language and religion are a specific semiotic systems, have a specific content, and reflect the external and internal world of humanity. In language, these qualities are reflected in different branches of linguistics, and in religion in the system of different religious ideas, since it is the founder of the formation of a social worldview, the establishment of clear rules not only in terms of everyday life, but also influenced the formation of history, geographical territories of peoples, development of science and language.

Used literature

<http://ziyonet.uz/>

Gadomsky A.K. Stylistic approach to the study of religious language / A.K. Gadomsky // Style-Beograd.2008.-No.7.-P.21-36.

Vinogradova L.N. Slavic folk demonology: problems of comparative study. - Moscow.: 2001.-95s.

Domakhina N. M. Demonic aesthetics in Russian art of the 19th - early 20th centuries: abstract. dis....cand. Phil. nauk.- St. Petersburg.: 2007.- 29c

Kositsyna N.O. Vocabulary of religious culture in the idiolect of A.A. Fet; Author's dissertation... Ph.D.-Kursk, 2011.-21s.

Losev A.F. Philosophy. Mythology. Culture.- Moscow.: 1991.-525c

Russell J.B. History of the concept of the devil.-Eurasia: 2000.-400s

Sharipov K.K. Structural and functional semantic features of the mythological dictionary in different languages: diss....cand. Phil.Sc. –Dushanbe: 2006.-141c

Shmelev D.N. Modern Russian dictionary. – Moscow: 2003.-366c

Blair J.M. De-demonizing the Old Testament: An Investigation of Azazel, Lilith, Deber, Qeteb and Reshef the Hebrew Bible: scient.res....Ph.D.: Edinburgh.: 2008.-287 p

СЎЗ САНЪАТИ ХАЛҚАРО ЖУРНАЛИ

6 ЖИЛД, 4 СОН

МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 4

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF WORD ART

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 4

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC The city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; E-mail: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000